

DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH MATERIAL

J. P. Dear, H. Arora, A. Puri and P. Hooper
Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College London, Exhibition road,
London, SW7 2AZ
j.dear@imperial.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Experiments have been performed on glass fibre sandwich specimens manufactured using a variety of different skin orientations and materials. Experimental results are described for quasi-static indentation, high speed impact and blast using digital image correlation (DIC) to identify failure mode development. The impact/blast resistance of these materials is of interest for marine and other structures.

Keywords: Digital image correlation, impact, blast, composite materials

INTRODUCTION

The research presented here investigates the failure mechanisms in various sandwich composite structures using Digital Image Correlation (DIC). The main benefits of composite sandwich materials are their high strength to weight ratio and low radar return. This has led to their increasing use in the marine sectors. Identifying the damage tolerance of existing and new sandwich constructions is valuable to many applications, for example, in evaluating the residual stealth properties after impact and for improved designs in military applications. Current designs of Fibre Reinforced Composites (FRC) structures use manufactured structural foams, such as PVC or polystyrene as the core. Furthermore, recent advances in flexible tooling have meant that new forms of glass fibre composite e.g. 3D woven material can be used as a cost effective skin material.

BACKGROUND TO DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION (DIC)

DIC is an optical non-contact technique for calculating displacement and strain fields of a deforming object. Here digital photography and white light illumination on a high contrast random surface paint pattern has used to trace full field surface displacements and strains. The DIC technique divides each image into overlapping quadrilateral facets. By matching facets across two calibrated cameras (3D DIC), with the camera positions known, displacements in all three dimensions can be calculated. Strain can also be calculated by analysing deformation of the facets over time. 2D DIC, with one camera, can be used to calculate strain fields provided there is no out-of-plane displacement present. Both 2D and 3D DIC methods were implemented during this study and during the following sections the capabilities of the two will be highlighted.

TYPES OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE TO BE INVESTIGATED

This investigation concentrates on distinguishing between the various continuous fibre weaves available. The 3 types covered here are: Conventional 2D Woven; 2D Stitched or Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) and 3D Woven.

Two Dimensional (2D) woven and Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF):

NCF usually consists of fibres placed parallel to each other (fibre tows) in separate plies of different orientation. These are then stitched together in their differing orientations using another type of fibre yarn (usually polyester), unlike conventional woven where the fibre tows are woven together themselves. The NCF produced results in a fabric with relatively zero crimp compared to conventional woven fabrics. This lay-up leads to in-plane properties of NCF being much improved relative to those conventional (2D) woven fabrics [1].

Orthogonal Three-dimensional (3D) Woven:

The structure of these fabrics differs greatly from conventional woven fabrics. They contain three groups of yarns in three mutually orthogonal directions: in-plane warp and weft yarn layers interlaced in the through-thickness direction by z-binder yarns. It is these z-binder yarns that provide the through-thickness reinforcement, which results in the high delamination resistance and high impact damage tolerance found in these fabrics relative to conventional 2D weaves. There are, however, notable disadvantages associated with the 3D weaving process. It has been found that the in-plane mechanical properties can be degraded due to fibre damage and potential misalignment during manufacture. This, in addition to the slight crimping of the fibres by the z-binder yarns, reduces the in-plane strength of the fabric [2 & 3].

EXPERIMENTS

To aid understanding of the failure processes, DIC can be performed during the various loading stages. A series of case studies have been conducted to prove the capabilities of the DIC technique. These case studies used ARAMIS to conduct both 2D and 3D DIC analyses of the behaviour of sandwich composite material over a range of strain rates from low rate impact (servo-hydraulic) to very high rate ballistics testing (blast/shock loading).

2D DIC: 4-Point Flexure

Experimentation: Four-point bend tests were performed on laboratory specimens to better understand the flexural behaviour of our sandwich material. The specimen geometries and loading configurations are given in Figure 1 and are compliant with ASTM C393-00 loading configurations [4], with all specimens having widths of 50 mm. For clarity these have been termed Type 1, which has thick skins and a thin core, Type 2, which has thin skins and a thick core and Type 3, which has thick skins and a thicker core. All of these types have multiple biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre layers with a PVC foam core. All tests were conducted at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 0.33 mm/s.

Figure 1: Sandwich panel loading configuration and cross-section dimensions (*Type 1*, *Type 2* and *Type 3*).

Results: The DIC evaluated bending strain (ϵ_x) plots are shown in Figure 2 for cross-head displacements of 5, 10 and 16 mm. For the *Type 1* specimen the strain is high underneath both inner and outer rollers as a result of foam core crushing. This is undesirable, yet between the inner rollers the distribution exhibits the usual compressive strain on the top surface and tensile strain on the lower surface. There is also a high level of strain in between the inner and outer rollers especially at the higher displacement levels. This is a result of the high levels of shear in that region. In contrast, the strain pattern for the *Type 2* specimen shows stronger indentation related strains underneath the inner rollers. This effect strongly influences the strain pattern between the inner rollers especially at the higher load levels. It is noticeable that in between the inner rollers there is some degree of typical bending strain, although it is much less defined than that seen with *Type 1* specimen. In addition to this, there is also a lack of high levels of strain in between the inner and outer rollers, which was observed with the *Type 1* results. This is because the indentation prohibits further bending, and further cross-head displacement simply adds to the indentation, and the panel is not deflected significantly.

Figure 2: ϵ_x for *Type 1* specimen (crosshead displacements of 5, 10 and 16 mm).

The results from the *Type 3* panel exhibit features of both the *Type 1* and *Type 2* panels because there is a high degree of indentation, but the core is still experiencing high levels of shear in between the inner and outer rollers. The most striking feature observed in the *Type 3* results is the strain concentration around the rollers, especially the inner rollers. This high level of strain is representative of indentation, but as the skins are thicker than the *Type 2* specimen the resultant strain shape is also quite different.

Effectively what has been demonstrated is that the indentation is less damaging with 2 mm thick skins compared to 1 mm thick skins. The differences between the specimen loading plots also reveal an interesting difference in material behaviour, Figure 3. There are similarities between the *Type 1* and *Type 3* results, as they both exhibit a plateau region. This is because the material, at its maximum load level, exhibits high degrees of shear in between the inner and outer roller to compensate for the increasing cross-head displacement. In contrast, the *Type 2* specimen shows a peak load, which then reduces as bending ceases. After this, the load increases marginally as a result of core densification underneath the inner rollers, as this is the only part of the specimen providing any further resistance to applied load. Both *Type 1* and *3* specimens failed by core shear fracture as shown in Figure 4. Examination of the event using DIC illustrates the capabilities of the technology. It is clear from the shear angle results that the failure was actually triggered by a high degree of shear along the adhesive line between the core and compressive (top) skin. It is believed that this was triggered by high levels of shear in the skin core bond line which itself was the result of the inner rollers pinning the skin at the contact point which a departure from the normal bending [5].

Figure 3: Load – displacement data for the three types of sandwich panel (vertical dotted lines are displacements from Figure 2.)

Both *Type 1* and *3* specimens failed by core shear fracture as shown in Figure 4. Examination of the event using DIC illustrates the capabilities of the technology. It is clear from the shear angle results that the failure was actually triggered by a high degree of shear along the adhesive line between the core and compressive (top) skin. It is believed that this was triggered by high levels of shear in the skin core bond line which itself was the result of the inner rollers pinning the skin at the contact point which a departure from the normal bending [5].

Figure 4: a) Core fracture of *Type 1* specimen; b) Core shear failure DIC sequence plot (shear angle).

This figure (above) shows where the foam core has fractured due to excessive shear. Examination of the event using DIC illustrates the capabilities of the technology. It is clear from the shear angle results that the failure was actually triggered by a high degree of shear along the adhesive line between the core and compressive (top) skin.

3D DIC: Low-Rate Impact

Experimentation: Sandwich composite panels were impacted at low rate using a truncated cone. The specimen geometries tested were 150mm x 150mm square panels. All of the specimens had multiple biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ glass fibre layers with a lightweight honeycomb core (sourced from HEXCEL). All tests were conducted at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 5 mm/s. The samples were clamped along their edges using a standard small-scale test frame. A schematic diagram of the experimental arrangement is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Schematic showing experimental arrangement: Side view of the specimen in the INSTRON testing machine (left) and a plan and edge view of the specimen and its retaining fixtures with dimensions (right).

The tests were conducted on an INSTRON Electromechanical testing machine. Force and displacement traces were recorded from the INSTRON. Two cameras were used to record the deformation of the panel during the test, to enable full field displacement and strain fields to be obtained using DIC technology. These tests were conducted to prove the 3D DIC technique prior to the high rate ballistics tests.

Results: A series of stage points were taken from the surface near the impactor and followed through the test, the data from one such point is shown in Figure 6. The graph illustrates the good correlation between the displacement recorded by the (cross-head displacement) INSTRON and those calculated by ARAMIS up until loading stage 9 (time = 9s), where the data begins to deviate. This is, however, only due to the stage points not being placed directly under the point of impact (since it was not visible).

Figure 6: Out-of-plane displacement compared between DIC results and those of the INSTRON (left) and the Force-Time trace of the sandwich composite (right).

Figure 7: Stage Images with contour plots overlaid showing the variation of: Out-of-plane displacement; Shear strain and Principal strain, where stage image = 1 relates to image at time = 1s etc.

From Figure 7 it can be noted that, following the early depression of the impacted specimen, the impact force is concentrated on the circumferential edge of the impactor contact face. This is evident when viewing the various displacement (and strain plots) produced by ARAMIS. This resulted in a failure process (skin wrinkling, cracking, core crushing prior to perforation) starting from the edge of the circular hole in the front skin. It is known that shear (and tensile) stresses play an important role in the energy absorption mechanisms within the composite [6]. Figure 7 shows how shear strain was the dominant contributor of strain, when comparing the shear and principal strains across each stage. Examination of the event using DIC highlights the sites of high shear and it is clear that the initial failure (front face cracking along 4 channels) was triggered by a high degree of shear.

3D DIC: High-Rate Ballistics Impact

Experimentation: Hardened ball bearings were fired using a 2m-long single-stage gas gun (see Figure 8) at sandwich composite samples at various velocities. The perforation process is essentially the same regardless of projectile shape in terms of ballistic limit and residual velocities [7]. Therefore the choice of 10mm diameter; 4.1g hardened steel ball bearing was made purely based on the fact that there is no energy lost to plastic deformation of the projectile, unlike when bullets are used typically. The gas gun propels a nylon sabot carrying the desired projectile down the barrel by release of a charge of compressed gas. Three high-speed cameras were employed during this study to allow for: 3D DIC analysis to be conducted on the front surfaces of the panels during impact, requiring two cameras; and velocity measurement of the projectile from a side-on view as it enters (and leaves) the target, requiring the final high-speed camera and images from this view can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 8: Picture of the gas-gun (left) and the sample fixture behind the polycarbonate shield (right)

Specimens were manufactured in a laboratory by RIFT (Resin Infusion using Flexible Tooling). The 3D woven specimens were manufactured with 1 ply of fabric per skin (100oz/yd² S2-glass and 96oz/yd² E2-glass sourced from 3TEX, with tests denoted by the initial S and E respectively) on a 10mm PVC core. The NCF specimens (25oz/yd², 2 layers $\pm 45^\circ$ of E2-glass sourced through Marineware, with tests denoted by N) were manufactured in a balanced symmetric lay-up. 4 plies of NCF were used per skin to match the areal weight of the 3D fabrics.

Results: From the data in Table 1 it can be seen that the 3D woven S2-glass performed the best out of the three selected weaves tested. It managed to stop the projectile from penetrating at all speeds tested. This result, or relative performance, was expected given the known properties of the S2-glass relative to E2-glass. Therefore the outcome amongst the 3D woven materials tested was expected. However, it was shown that the NCF performed better at absorbing energy compared to its 3D woven E2-glass counterpart. This is thought to be due to the slight crimping observed in the 3D weave from the z-binder yarn.

Table 1: Velocity recordings and energy absorption on Impact.

Test Number	Initial Velocity m/s	Final Velocity m/s	Absorbed Energy J
N1	240	0	116
S1	240	0	116
E1	240	0	116
N2	261	0	136
S2	271	0	146
E2	301	80	168
N3	301	80	168
S3	331	0	219
E3	331	165	164
N4	361	150	215
S4	331	0	219
E4	301	225	79

The main reason for the z-binder yarn is to improve the delamination resistance of the composite. However this seems to limit the modes of energy dissipation. The damage area in the 3D weaves remains relatively constant and localised around the impact zone (see Figure 10). Therefore the structural integrity of the composite may remain relatively high (this should be tested in a compression after impact analysis) but in the

case of 3D woven E2-glass its ballistic resistance appears below that of the NCF counterpart.

Figure 9: Sample stages taken from side-on to record the incident and exit velocities. Images were recorded every 83μs by the high-speed camera.

It is thought that de-bonding between lower skins and core decreases with increase in impact velocity, whilst the delamination in the lower skins in particular increases with increasing impact velocity [7]. This was observed in post test sample inspection across each velocity tested, an example of such inspection is given in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Sample images of the back face deformation/damage observed in the NCF tests N1, N4 and 3D woven E2-glass test E4 (left to right).

Another factor to consider is how the velocity of the impact can affect the composite behaviour. From literature it is stated that at higher impact velocities, the mechanisms of energy absorption remain the same for sandwich panels irrespective of the panel thickness/projectile thickness ratios and that kinetic energy is mainly dissipated in the FRP laminate skins [7]. This should allow the interpretation of the strain field on the surface to reflect a greater significance on impact behaviour. The graph in Figure 11 was created by tracking points close to the point of impact over the duration of the test. The z-displacement (location) is then plotted over time (or strain stage, where the interval between stages lasts 124μs). It can be seen from the graph that all energy absorbed was dissipated within a period of 25 stages or ~3ms. In this case, all kinetic energy from the projectile was absorbed by the panel (no complete penetration

observed). The images show clearly the change in z-displacement observed during the early stages of response. The images shown in Figure 12 highlight the state of strain that is created in the composite.

Figure 11: Graph illustrating the dynamic nature of the impact and the contours of the z-displacement overlaid onto the deformed image stages (Test S2).

The impact causes a tensile wave to propagate outwards from the site of impact, inducing a state of shear at 45°. It is known that energy absorption occurs due to various mechanisms (such as matrix/fibre damage, fibre pull out or delamination), which can be a result of tensile or shear stresses [6]. These images provide visual evidence of such stress states. However, further work is required to assess these postulations in detail. These tests formed a preliminary assessment of the DIC technique being implemented in such test conditions. These tests show that in spite of the potential debris expelled upon impact (fragmentation), more than half the field can be analysed using this technique.

Figure 12: Sample images of the shear strain contours overlaid on the deformed image stages for test 5 (left) and test 11 (right).

One improvement will be to use a faster rate of image sampling to capture the change in strain during the course of the projectile's journey through each ply. Here we are making general observations of the panel behaviour during arbitrary stages of the impact event.

3D DIC: Blast Trials

Experimentation: Blast testing of FRC sandwich panels is scheduled for June 2009. Panels sized 1.5m x 1.2m of varying core thickness will be subjected to blast loading to assess the blast resistance of these structures as well as the influence of core thickness.

Similar blast testing has been conducted on laminated glass at RAF Spadeadam using C-4 charges. Two 1.5m x 1.2m windows were tested at a time on a purpose built concrete test pad. The laminated glass used was a symmetrical layup of annealed glass and a PVB interlayer. The thickness of the laminate was 3mm/1.52mm/3mm for the three layers respectively. Stand-off distance and charge weight was varied to control the loading pressure on the windows. Deformation of the window was captured with two high-speed video cameras from inside the cubicle. The window was painted to block out light from the explosion and a speckle pattern was applied to the rear face so deformation could be calculated using DIC methods.

Figure 13: The test cubicle with an explosive charge at a specified stand-off distance (left) and a typical detonation (right).

Results: A photograph of a typical explosive set-up and detonation is shown in the Figure 13. The inset shows the laminated glass in front of the cubicle, deformed and detached from the frame. Failure of the silicone joint retaining the window was the predominant failure mode during the trials. Results from the DIC analysis are shown in Figure 14. The rectangular shape of the contour lines is typical for an impulsive loading case. A maximum displacement of approximately 200mm is seen before pull out. The patterns on the strain plots result from strain concentrating around the edges of the glass fragments, where the PVB layer bridges the gap between fragments.

Figure 14: Unprocessed images alongside the analysed results from ARAMIS.

CONCLUSION

DIC of experiments performed on sandwich materials has been conducted. Results from these highlighted the causes for the onset of failure in the composite materials. Impact and indentation of specimens with varied composition is being thoroughly investigated, with the DIC technique proving proficient in aiding the failure diagnosis of composites across a broad range of strain rates. As the specimens are manufactured using RIFT, the results are related to the use of these materials for marine, wind turbines, building and similar applications. Continuing research studies are addressing blast and other high loading conditions. Such information will allow for a constructive evaluation of the blast resistance and strength after blast of a variety of glass fibre skin orientations and materials.

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